

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 9

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 9

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁰ For the choir director; on Muth-labben. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>9:1 . לְמִנְצַחַת עַל־מִוֹת לַיָּן מִזְמוֹר</p>
<p>¹ I will give thanks to the LORD with all my heart; I will tell of all Your wonders.</p>	<p>לְדָוָד : ² אֹרְתָה יְהוָה בְּכָל־לִבִּי</p>
<p>² I will be glad and exult in You; I will sing praise to Your name, O Most High.</p>	<p>אֶסְפְּרָה כָּל־נִפְלְאוֹתֶיךָ : ³ אֲשַׁמְחָה וְאֶעֱלֶצָה בְּךָ אֲזַמְרָה שִׁמְךָ עֲלִיּוֹן : ⁴ בְּשׁוֹב־אוֹיְבֵי</p>
<p>³ When my enemies turn back, They stumble and perish before You.</p>	<p>אֶחָזֵר יִכָּשְׁלוּ וַיֵּאבְדוּ מִפְּנֵיךָ : ⁵</p>
<p>⁴ For You have maintained my just cause; You have sat on the throne judging righteously.</p>	<p>כִּי־עָשִׂיתָ מִשְׁפָּטִי וְדִינִי יִשְׁבֹּתָ</p>
<p>⁵ You have rebuked the nations, You have destroyed the wicked; You have blotted out their name forever and ever.</p>	<p>לְכֹפֵא שׁוֹפֵט צָדֵק : ⁶ גָּעַרְתָּ</p>
<p>⁶ The enemy has come to an end in perpetual ruins, And You have uprooted the cities; The very memory of them has perished.</p>	<p>גּוֹיִם אֲבַדְתָּ רָשָׁע שָׁמָם מְחִיתָ</p>
<p>⁷ But the LORD abides forever; He has established His throne for judgment,</p>	<p>לְעוֹלָם וָעֶד : ⁷ הָאֵלֹהִים אֶתְמוֹ</p>
<p>⁸ And He will judge the world in righteousness; He will execute judgment for the peoples with equity.</p>	<p>תָּרֵבֹת לַנִּצְחָת וְעָרִים נִתְּשַׁתָּ</p>
<p>⁹ The LORD also will be a stronghold for the oppressed, A stronghold in times of trouble;</p>	<p>אֲבָד זְכָרָם הִמָּחָה : ⁸ וַיְהִי־הוּא</p>
<p>¹⁰ And those who know Your name will put their trust in You, For You, O LORD, have not forsaken those who seek You.</p>	<p>לְעוֹלָם יֵשֵׁב כּוֹנֵן לְמִשְׁפָּט</p>
<p>¹¹ Sing praises to the LORD, who dwells in Zion; Declare among the peoples His deeds.</p>	<p>כִּסְאוֹ : ⁹ וְהוּא יִשְׁפֹּט־תֵּבֵל</p>
	<p>בְּצִדְקַת יָדָיו לְאֲמִיִּם בְּמִישְׁפָּרִים :</p>
	<p>¹⁰ וַיְהִי יְהוָה מִשְׁגָּב לְהֵדָה מִשְׁגָּב</p>
	<p>לְעַתּוֹת בַּצָּרָה : ¹¹ וַיִּבְטְחוּ בְּךָ</p>
	<p>יִדְעֵי שִׁמְךָ כִּי לֹא־עָזַבְתָּ</p>
	<p>דַּרְשֵׁיךָ יְהוָה : ¹² זָמְרוּ לַיהוָה</p>
	<p>יֵשֵׁב צִיּוֹן תִּגְדְּרוּ בְּעַמִּים</p>
	<p>עַל־לוֹתֵיךָ : ¹³ כִּי־דַרְשׁוּ־מִים</p>

¹² For He who requires blood remembers them; He does not forget the cry of the afflicted.

¹³ Be gracious to me, O LORD; See my affliction from those who hate me, You who lift me up from the gates of death,

¹⁴ That I may tell of all Your praises, That in the gates of the daughter of Zion I may rejoice in Your salvation.

¹⁵ The nations have sunk down in the pit which they have made; In the net which they hid, their own foot has been caught.

¹⁶ The LORD has made Himself known; He has executed judgment. In the work of his own hands the wicked is snared. Higgsaion Selah.

¹⁷ The wicked will return to Sheol, *Even* all the nations who forget God.

¹⁸ For the needy will not always be forgotten, Nor the hope of the afflicted perish forever.

¹⁹ Arise, O LORD, do not let man prevail; Let the nations be judged before You.

²⁰ Put them in fear, O LORD; Let the nations know that they are but men. Selah.

אוֹתָם זָכַר לֹא־שָׁכַח צְעָקָתָם
עֲנִיִּים [עֲנִיִּים:] ¹⁴ חָנְנֵנִי יְהוָה
רַחֵם עָנְיִי מִשֹּׂנְאֵי מְרוֹמָי
מִשְׁעַרֵי מָוֶת: ¹⁵ לִמְעַן אֲסַפְּרָה
כָּל־תְּהִלָּתֶיךָ בְּשַׁעְרֵי בֵּת־צִיּוֹן
אֲגִידָה בִּישׁוּעָתְךָ: ¹⁶ טָבְעוּ
גוֹיִם בְּשַׁחַת עָשׂוּ בְּרֶשֶׁת־זוֹ
טָמְנוּ נִלְכְּדָה רַגְלָם: ¹⁷ נֹדַע |
יְהוָה מִשְׁפָּט עָשָׂה בְּפַעַל כַּפְּיוֹ
נִזְקַשׁ רָשָׁע הַגִּזּוֹן סִלָּה: ¹⁸
יָשׁוּבוּ רָשָׁעִים לְשֹׂאֵלָה כָּל־
גוֹיִם שְׁכַחֵי אֱלֹהִים: ¹⁹ כִּי לֹא
לִנְצַח יִשְׁכַּח אֲבִיוֹן הַקְּנֹת עֲנִיִּים
[עֲנִיִּים] תֵּאבְדַר לְעַד: ²⁰ קוֹמָה
יְהוָה אֶל־יַעֲזוּ אֲנֹשׁ יִשְׁפֹּטוּ גוֹיִם
עַל־פְּנֵיךָ: ²¹ שִׁיתָה יְהוָה |
מוֹרָה לָתֵם יִדְעוּ גוֹיִם אֲנֹשׁ
תִּמָּה סִלָּה:

Targum

¹ For praise, concerning the death of the man who went out between the armies. A hymn of David. [ANOTHER TARGUM: For praise, concerning the sweetness of the sound by a son. A hymn of David.] ² I will sing praise in the LORD's presence with all my heart; I will tell all of your miracles. ³ I will be glad and rejoice in your word; I will praise your name, O Most High. ⁴ When my enemies turn back, they will stumble and perish before you. ⁵ Because you have accomplished my vindication and my judgment; you sat down on the throne of the righteous judge. ⁶ You rebuked the peoples of the Philistines; you destroyed Goliath the wicked; their name you erased forever and ever. ⁷ And when the enemy fell, his forces were obliterated, and their fortresses were laid waste forever, and as for their cities, you destroyed the memory of them forever. ⁸ But as for the word of the LORD, his seat is in the highest heaven forever; he has established his throne for judgment. ⁹ And he shall judge the people of the earth in righteousness; he will judge the Gentiles in uprightness. ¹⁰ And the word of the LORD will be strength to the poor, strength in times of distress. ¹¹ And those who know your name will look at your hope, because you have not abandoned those who seek you, O LORD. ¹² Sing praise before the LORD who made his presence rest in Zion; tell his deeds among the Gentiles. ¹³ For he avenges the innocent blood; he remembers the, he does not neglect the complaint of the humble. ¹⁴ Pity me, O LORD; see my pain caused by my enemies, you who lift me up from the entrances of death. ¹⁵ So that I may tell all your praises in the entrances of the gates of the assembly of Zion; I will exult in your redemption. ¹⁶ The peoples have sunk in the pit that they made; in the very net they concealed, their feet are caught. ¹⁷ Manifest before the LORD is the judgement he executed: through the works of his hands, the wicked man stumbled, the righteous will rejoice forever. ¹⁸ The wicked will return to Sheol, all the Gentiles who neglected the fear of the LORD. ¹⁹ For the needy man is not forever neglected; the hope of the humble will not perish forever. ²⁰ Arise, O LORD, may the wicked son of man not grow strong, may the Gentiles be judged in your presence. ²¹ Put, O LORD, fear on them; let the peoples know that they are a son of man forever.

Interlinear

Psa. 9:0 For the choir director on

Key
Lex
PrtSpeech

Muth-labben A Psalm of David

Psa. 9:1 I will give thanks to

Key
Lex
PrtSpeech
H3034 יָדָה
H3034 יָדָה
Verb Verb

the Lord with all my heart I will
H3068 יהוה Noun
H3605 כל Noun
H3820 לֵב Noun

tell of all Your wonders
H5608 סָפַר Verb
H3605 כל Noun
H6381 פָּלֵא Verb

Psa. 9:2 I will be glad and exult in You
Key
Lex
PrtSpeech
H8055 שָׂמַח Verb
H5970 עָלֵץ Verb

I will sing praise to Your name O Most High
H2167 זָמַר Verb
H2167 זָמַר Verb
H8034 שֵׁם Noun
H5945b עָלִיז Adj.
H5945b עָלִיז Adj.

Psa. 9:3 When my enemies
Key
Lex
PrtSpeech
H0340 אֹיֵב Noun

turn back They stumble and perish before

H7725	H0268	H3782	H0006
שוב	אָהוּר	פָּשַׁל	אָבַד
Verb	Noun	Verb	Verb

before	before	You
H4480	H6440	
בֵּין	פְּנִים	
Part.	Noun	

Psa. 9:4	For	You	have	maintained	my
Key				H6213a	
Lex				עָשָׂה	
PrtSpeech				Verb	

just	cause	You	have	sat	on	the	throne
H4941	H1779			H3427			H3678
מִשְׁפָּט	דִּין			יָשַׁב			כִּסֵּא
Noun	Noun			Verb			Noun

judging	righteously
H8199	H6664
שָׁפַט	צְדָקָה
Verb	Noun

Psa. 9:5	You	have	rebuked	the	nations
Key			H1605		H1471
Lex			נָעַר		גּוֹי
PrtSpeech			Verb		Noun

You	have	destroyed	the	wicked	You	have
		H0006		H7563		
		אָבַד		רָשָׁע		
		Verb		Adj.		

blotted	out	their	name	forever	and	ever
H4229a			H8034	H5769		H5703
מָחָה			שֵׁם	עוֹלָם		עַד
Verb			Noun	Noun		Noun

Psa. 9:6	The	enemy	has	come
Key		H0340		H8552
Lex		אֹיֵב		הִתְמַם
PrtSpeech		Noun		Verb

to	an	end	in	perpetual	ruins	And	You	have	uprooted
		H8552		H5331	H2723				H5428
		תָּמַם		נֶצַח	תְּרָבָה				נָתַשׁ
		Verb		Noun	Noun				Verb

the	cities	The	very	memory	of	them	has
	H5892b		H1992a	H2143			
	עִיר		הֵם	זְכָר			
	Noun		Pron.	Noun			

perished
H0006
אָבַד
Verb

Psa. 9:7	But	the	Lord
Key			H3068
Lex			יְהוָה
PrtSpeech			Noun

abides	forever	He	has	established	His
H3427	H5769			H3559	
יָשַׁב	עוֹלָם			כּוֹן	
Verb	Noun			Verb	

throne	for	judgment
H3678		H4941
כִּסֵּא		מִשְׁפָּט
Noun		Noun

Psa. 9:8	And	He	will	judge	the	world	in
Key				H8199		H8398	
Lex				שָׁפַט		תִּבְלָ	
PrtSpeech				Verb		Noun	

righteousness	He	will	execute	judgment	for	the
H6664			H1777	H1777		
צְדָקָה			דִּין	דִּין		
Noun			Verb	Verb		

peoples	with	equity
H3816		H4339

לְאֵם
Noun

מִיֶּשֶׁר
Noun

Psa. 9:9 The Lord also will be a
Key H3068
Lex יְהוָה
PrtSpeech Noun

stronghold for the oppressed A stronghold in times of
H4869 H1790 H4869 H6256
מִשְׁנֵב דָּד מִשְׁנֵב עַתָּה
Noun Adj. Noun Noun

trouble
H6869a
צָרָה
--

Psa. 9:10 And those who know Your
Key H3045
Lex יָדַע
PrtSpeech Verb

name will put their trust in You For You O Lord
H8034 H0982 H0982 H0982 H3068
שֵׁם בָּטַח בָּטַח יְהוָה
Noun Verb Verb Noun

have not forsaken those who seek You
H5800a H1875
עָזַב דָּרַשׁ
Verb Verb

Psa. 9:11 Sing praises to the
Key H2167 H2167
Lex זָמַר זָמַר
PrtSpeech Verb Verb

Lord who dwells in Zion
H3068 H3427 H6726
יְהוָה יָשַׁב צִיּוֹן
Noun Verb Noun

Declare among the peoples His deeds
 H5046 H5971a H5949
 נָגַד עַם עֲלֵיָהָ
 Verb Noun Noun

Psa. 9:12 For He who requires blood
 Key H1875 H1818
 Lex דָּרַשׁ דָּם
 PrtSpeech Verb Noun

remembers them He does not forget the cry of the
 H2142 H7911 H6818
 זָכַר שָׁכַח שָׁעָקָה
 Verb Verb Noun

afflicted
 H6035
 עָנָו
 Adj.

Psa. 9:13 Be gracious to me O Lord
 Key H2603a H3068
 Lex הִנֵּן יְהוָה
 PrtSpeech Verb Noun

See my affliction from those who hate me You
 H7200 H6040a H8130
 רָאָה עָנִי שָׂנֵא
 Verb Noun Verb

who lift me up from the gates of death
 H7311 H8179 H4194
 רוּם שַׁעַר מָוֶת
 Verb Noun Noun

Psa. 9:14 That I may tell of all Your
 Key H5608 H3605
 Lex סַפַּר כָּל
 PrtSpeech Verb Noun

praises That in the gates of the daughter of Zion
 H8416 H8179 H1323 H6726
 תְּהַלֵּל שַׁעַר בַּת צִיּוֹן

	Noun			Noun		Noun		Noun		
I	may	rejoice H1523 גִּיל Verb	in	Your	salvation H3444 יְשׁוּעָה Noun					
	Psa. 9:15 Key Lex PrtSpeech		The	nations H1471 גוֹי Noun	have	sunk H2883 טָבַע Verb	down	H2883 טָבַע Verb		
in	the	pit H7845 שַׁחַת Noun	which	they	have	made H6213a עָשָׂה Verb	In	the		
net H7568 רֶשֶׁת Noun	which H2098 זוֹ Part.		they	hid H2934 טָמְנוּ Verb	their	own	foot H7272 רֵגְלִי Noun	has	been	
caught H3920 לָכַד Verb										
	Psa. 9:16 Key Lex PrtSpeech		The	Lord H3068 יְהוָה Noun	has	made H3045 יָדַע Verb	Himself			
known H3045 יָדַע Verb	He	has	executed H6213a עָשָׂה Verb	judgment H4941 מִשְׁפָּט Noun						
In	the	work H6467 פֶּעַל Noun	of	his	own	hands H3709 כַּף Noun	the	wicked H7563 רָשָׁע Adj.	is	snared H5367 נָקַשׁ Verb
Higgaion	Selah									

H1902
הַגִּיּוֹן
Noun

H5542
סָלָה
Part.

Psa. 9:17
Key
Lex
PrtSpeech

The wicked will
H7563
רָשָׁע
Adj.

return
H7725
שׁוּב
Verb

to Sheol
H7585
שְׁאוֹל
Noun

Even all
H3605
כָּל
Noun

the nations
H1471
גוֹי
Noun

who
H7913
שָׂכָח
Adj.

forget
H7913
שָׂכָח
Adj.

God
H0430
אֱלֹהִים
Noun

Psa. 9:18
Key
Lex
PrtSpeech

For the needy
H0034
אֶבְיֹוֹן
Adj.

will not always be
H5331
נָצַח
Noun

forgotten
H7911
שָׂכַח
Verb

Nor the hope
H8615b
תְּקוּוּהָ
Noun

of the afflicted
H6041
עָנִי
Adj.

perish
H0006
אָבַד
Verb

forever
H5703
עַד
Noun

Psa. 9:19
Key
Lex
PrtSpeech

Arise O
H6965
קוּם
Verb

Lord
H3068
יְהוָה
Noun

do not let

man prevail
H0582
אָנֹשׁ
Noun

Let the
H5810
עָזָז
Verb

nations	be	judged	before	You
H1471		H8199		
גוֹי		שָׁפַט		
Noun		Verb		

Psa. 9:20	Put	them	in	fear	O
Key	H7896			H4177b	
Lex	שִׁית			מוֹדָה	
PrtSpeech	Verb			Noun	

Lord	Let	the	nations	know	that	they	are	but
H3068			H1471	H3045				
יְהוָה			גוֹי	יָדַע				
Noun			Noun	Verb				

men	Selah
H0582	H5542
אָנוּשׁ	סֵלָה
Noun	Part.

Superscript

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
0 For the choir director; on Muth-labben. A Psalm of David.	לְמִנְצַחַת עֲלֻמוֹת לְבֵן מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד

Superscript Analysis

עֲלֻמוֹת לְבֵן (al'mut laben) – means “on the death of the son.” In several Hebrew versions of this Psalm, this phrase is written עֲלֻ-מוֹת לְבֵן which corresponds to the actual translation. The WTT version connects *al* and *mut*. This is because the Sages do not believe that the translation “on the death of the son” fits this phrase. This Psalm does not talk about death. The Sage Rashi observed that since the Psalm does not indicate death, the phrase must mean something else. This superscript could be saying that immortality will be given to Israel because Israel is the only nation that submitted willingly to the guidance of the LORD and acceptance of His Torah.

The Psalm addresses the nation of Israel and not an individual. *Laben* refers to Israel's relationship to the LORD.

The Psalm expresses the historical events of Israel during their wanderings among the peoples of the world. Throughout Israel's history, it has suffered trials and tribulations. Larger nations have left a trail of ruins upon their paths to military victories, and it was Israel who suffered at their hands.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the LORD, who grants Netzach in the form of immortality to the nation of Israel.

A psalm of David.

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
¹ I will give thanks to the LORD with all my heart; I will tell of all Your wonders.	² אֲדַבֵּר יְהוָה בְּכָל-לִבִּי אֲסַפְּרָה כָּל-נִפְלְאוֹתֶיךָ

Verse Analysis

בְּכָל-לִבִּי (b'kal leebee) means “all my heart.” The Psalmist is saying that we need to recognize the LORD with all our being. This act was considered a great miracle when Israel first became a nation, and the LORD revealed His greatness to them.

David’s victory over Goliath was an important event in Israel’s history, and because the LORD granted David victory, He deserves full-hearted praise.

A basic credo of Judaism is that one must praise the LORD in good and bad times. An appreciation for the LORD is necessary all the time.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

I will always praise you, LORD, and tell the nations of your wondrous works in good and bad times.

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
2 I will be glad and exult in You; I will sing praise to Your name, O Most High.	אֲשַׁמְּחָהּ וְאֶעֱלֶזָה בְּךָ אֲזַמְּרָה 3 שִׁמְךָ עֲלִיזוֹן :

Verse Analysis

אֲשַׁמְּחָהּ (as'm'cha) means “to rejoice.” This is a frame of mind that can recognize that which is good and true. One comes closer to the LORD through duty fulfilled.

Exulting the LORD gave David confidence when he faced Goliath. Therefore, if one exalts the LORD, one will gain confidence in everything that life offers.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

I rejoice and sing praises to your name, O most high.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
3 When my enemies turn back, They stumble and perish before You.	בְּשׁוּב-אֹיְבֵי אַחֲזֹר יִכָּשְׁלוּ 4 וַיִּאָבְדוּ מִפְּנֵיךָ

Verse Analysis

When the Philistines retreated after David slew Goliath, the Psalmist said that they stumbled and crawled back to their homeland. When David beat Goliath, it was not the power of David which prevailed; it was the power of the LORD through David, which prevailed. The Philistines saw the power and might of the LORD through David.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

When Goliath was slain, the Philistines stumbled back home because they were in fear of Gevurah. Justice for Israel was being served because of the Philistines oppression.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
4 For You have maintained my just cause; You have sat on the throne judging righteously.	כִּי־עָשִׂיתָ מִשְׁפָּטַי וְדִינִי יִשְׁבֶּהָ לְכִסֵּא שׁוֹפֵט צְדָק :

Verse Analysis

Israel's nation was dependent solely upon the spiritual perception of truth and the honorable discharge of life's duties, all subordinated to the LORD. The nations that surrounded Israel were opposed to them because they were based on materialism. Therefore, Israel represents the spiritual world in Malkhut. In contrast, the rest of the nations of the world represent the material world in Malkhut. Only in Malkhut can the spiritual and material world connect.

Every time a kingdom is built, which neglects moral Law and is based on violence, it eventually crumbles and perishes. When a nation's goal is material possessions, it will not last the test of time. Israel depended on the LORD, which brought them into a spiritual connection with the LORD.

When Goliath met David on the battlefield, he cursed the name of the LORD. The LORD sent Gevurah to execute justice on Goliath and the Philistines. People today need to learn the lesson of the Philistines. When the material world is more important than the spiritual world, Gevurah will reject them when learning Malkhut and entering Yesod. Materialistic people who ignore the LORD do not have a place in the Tree of Life.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

You have furthered my destiny and appointed Gevruah to bring the judgment seat for judging righteously.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁵ You have rebuked the nations, You have destroyed the wicked; You have blotted out their name forever and ever.</p>	<p>וְעִרְתָּ גּוֹיִם אִפְרַת רָשָׁע שְׁמָם⁶ : מְחִיתָ לְעוֹלָם וְעַד :</p>

Verse Analysis

When the LORD strikes down a lawless kingdom, it is a warning to the rest of the world’s kingdoms to leave their evil. Immoral kingdoms will be destroyed b the LORD if they do not destroy themselves because of their wickedness. The Psalmist could also be talking about what was going to happen to Israel when she decided to stop following the Torah’s moral Law and became like the nations that surrounded her. Israel must always survive because of the LORD’s promise to Abraham.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

For you have told the nations of the world that lawlessness and immorality will eventually bring Gevurah to the nation, and the nation will be erased from history.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
6 The enemy has come to an end in perpetual ruins, And You have uprooted the cities; The very memory of them has perished.	הָאֹיֵב אֶתְמוּן חֲרָבוֹת לְנֹצֶת ⁷ וְעָרִים נִתְשָׁת אֲבָד זְכָרָם הִמָּחָה :

Verse Analysis

When a nation or kingdom is destroyed, it is generally erased from history. David continues to talk about the end of kingdoms that have been immoral. The memory of the wicked nations perishes overtime.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The enemy's kingdom has come to an end forever. You destroyed their cities, and they have been removed from history and thus forgotten.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
7 But the LORD abides forever; He has established His throne for judgment,	8 וַיֵּהָרֶה לְעוֹלָם יֵשֵׁב כּוֹנֵן לְמִשְׁפָּט כְּסֹאֵוֹ :

Verse Analysis

The LORD is resting until that future date when Gevurah's day of judgment arrives. The events of the world are preparations for said day. The Sage Rashi said that only after the eradication of Amalek the LORD's throne and name will be complete. The war against Amalek can be found in Exodus 17:16

The LORD has sworn; the LORD will have war against Amalek from generation to generation. (Exodus 17:16)

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD is resting until the defeat of Amalek, for when that happens, Gevurah will judge the world from His throne.

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
8 And He will judge the world in righteousness; He will execute judgment for the peoples with equity	וְהוּא יִשְׁפֹּט-תֵּבֵל בְּצֶדֶק יִדְיִן׃ לְאֲמֹיִם בְּמִישְׁקִים׃

Verse Analysis

וְהוּא יִשְׁפֹּט (v'hu yeesh'fot) – means “He will judge.” This phrase denotes humankind’s world, with all its chaos, following a stable course of development. One day the chaos of the world will be transformed into order by Gevurah (justice). Gevurah will bring justice by measuring all human affairs against the heavenly standard of justice.

If the world followed an international law founded upon mutual respect as the LORD demands, the outcome would be permanent peace on Earth.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

And Gevurah will judge the world and will bring order to chaos through executing judgment upon the nations.

Verse Nine

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
9 The LORD also will be a stronghold for the oppressed, A stronghold in times of trouble;	10 וְיִהְיֶה יְהוָה מְשֻׁבָּב לְרֵד מְשֻׁבָּב לְעֵתוֹת בְּצָרָה׃

Verse Analysis

שָׁפֵט (shapet) – means “to judge.” “The primary sense of שָׁפֵט is to exercise the processes of government. However, since the ancients did not always divide the functions of government, as most modern governments do, between legislative, executive, and judicial functions (and departments), the common translation, “to judge,” misleads us. For, the word, judge, as שָׁפֵט is usually translated, in modern English, means to exercise only the judicial function of government.” (TWOT) It can also denote a high tower for the afflicted. The LORD will bring judgment against a government that oppresses its people.

Everything takes time to develop. At times the people of Israel wondered where the LORD was. Why did the LORD not help them? Sometimes it takes time for the LORD to react to injustice. This is because the LORD gives people time to repent.

When the LORD is ready for global judgment, He will correct the injustice that was done to Israel. The Sage Radak said that the moment of great distress was when the Philistines threatened to destroy Israel. The threat was the greatest during the battle when David killed Goliath.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD shall become a high tower for the oppressed and afflicted and for those times of future distress.

Verse Ten

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁰ And those who know Your name will put their trust in You, For You, O LORD, have not forsaken those who seek You.</p>	<p>וַיִּבְטְחוּ בְךָ יוֹדְעֵי שְׁמֶךָ כִּי לֹא־¹¹ עָזַבְתָּ רוֹשְׁעִי יְהוָה׃</p>

Verse Analysis

Those who are being oppressed will wait patiently because they know the Name of the LORD. The people were sustained by the knowledge of His nature and His will. The people will not lose hope because they know the LORD is always with them and will bring justice.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The oppressed people who know the LORD's name shall always trust You; You have never forsaken all people who seek out your counsel and help for you.

Verse Eleven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
¹¹ Sing praises to the LORD, who dwells in Zion; Declare among the peoples His deeds.	זַמְרוּ לַיהוָה יֹשֵׁב צִיּוֹן ¹² : תִּגְדְּדוּ בְּעַמִּים עֲלִילוֹתָיו :

Verse Analysis

The Temple of the LORD was built in Zion, and the people believed that the LORD dwelt there. The Shekinah lived in the Temple, the presence of the LORD. When the people sinned to the point when the LORD brought the Babylonians into Judah, He removed the Shekinah from the Temple. When that happened, the Babylonians destroyed the city and the Temple.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Sing praises to the LORD who dwells in the Temple in Zion, and declare His works among the nations.

Verse Twelve

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
¹² For He who requires blood remembers them; He does not forget the cry of the afflicted.	כִּי־דָרַשׁ דָּמַיִם אֹתָם זָכַר לֹא־ נִשְׁכַּח צַעֲקַת עֲנִיִּים [עֲנָוִים:]

Verse Analysis

[עֲנָוִים:] עֲנִיִּים (aneeyeeym) (anaveem) – means “poor” and “humble.” The word “poor” is misspelled in this Psalm, and the misspelled word means “humble.” Hirsch said that this Psalm was written this way, with both words, to understand why the humble are made to suffer. The humble are dependent on higher powers and powerless to defend themselves. The humble were made to suffer to experience firsthand the pain of oppression by despots’ heels. The despots should have learned that humane treatment is what the LORD wants for all people, especially Israel.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

For the LORD, avenges blood has remembered them; He has not forgotten the cry of the humble.

Verse Thirteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
13 Be gracious to me, O LORD; See my affliction from those who hate me, You who lift me up from the gates of death,	14 חַנּוּנִי יְהוָה רְאֵה עֲנִי מִשְׁנֵאֵי מְרוֹמָי מִשְׁעַרֵי מוֹת :

Verse Analysis

The first word is unique in that it has three נ in it. The word comes from the word חָנַן (*hānan*), which means “to be gracious; to show pity.” The Sage Alshich explained that the three *nun* letters are unusual. It shows that David asked the LORD for a generous portion of mercy.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Favor me, LORD. See my afflictions and give me a generous portion of mercy for you alone raise me above death’s door.

Verse Fourteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁴ That I may tell of all Your praises, That in the gates of the daughter of Zion I may rejoice in Your salvation</p>	<p>15 לְמַעַן אֲסַפְּרָה כָּל-תְּהִלָּתֶיךָ בְּשַׁעַרֵי בֵּית-צִיּוֹן אֲגִידָה בִּישׁוּעָתֶךָ :</p>

Verse Analysis

David said that when he is saved from his enemies, he will go to the gates of Zion to offer his thanksgiving because that is where the Shekinah resides.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

That I may tell of Your acts and that I may take one-day rejoice within the gates of Zion, so that I may rejoice in your salvation.

Verse Fifteen & Sixteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁵ The nations have sunk down in the pit which they have made; In the net which they hid, their own foot has been caught.</p> <p>¹⁶ The LORD has made Himself known; He has executed judgment. In the work of his own hands the wicked is snared. Higgsaion Selah.</p>	<p>¹⁶ טָבַעְנוּ גּוֹיִם בְּשִׁחַת עֲשׂוּיָהּ בְּרִשְׁת־צֶדֶק טָמְנוּ נֶלְכְּדָה רַגְלָם׃ נֹרֵעַ אִיהוָה מִשְׁפָּט עֲשָׂה׃¹⁷ בְּפִעַל בְּפִיּוֹ נֹקֵשׁ רָשָׁע הַגִּיּוֹן׃ סֵלָה׃</p>

Verse Analysis

We can see a sign of the LORD’s judgment whenever a wicked person gets caught in the trap of his/her own treacherous tricks.

הַגִּיּוֹן (heegaryon) – “means “meditation, whispering, melody. “The noun הַגִּיּוֹן refers to the music of a harp in Psalm 92:3. Possibly a musical notation is meant by the “Higgsaion” in 9:16 [H 17], but “meditation” is an alternate interpretation.” (TWOT)

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

V16 – Whenever a nation falls into their own evil pit, into the very snare they caught their foot in,

V17 – The LORD becomes known because He sends Gevurah to execute judgment. Meditate on these two verses.

Verse Seventeen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
¹⁷ The wicked will return to Sheol, <i>Even</i> all the nations who forget God.	יָשׁוּבוּ רְשָׁעִים לְשֵׁאוֹלָה כָּל־ גּוֹיִם שָׁכְחֵי אֱלֹהִים׃

Verse Analysis

יָשׁוּבוּ רְשָׁעִים לְשֵׁאוֹלָה (yashuvu reshaeem leesheola) – means “the wicked will return to Sheol.” Hirsch said this is not what the verse is saying. The wicked returning to Sheol presupposes that they have been in the grave once before. Instead, it means “they shall retreat to Sheol.” They will sink back from the heights that they have climbed back to Sheol. The word **שֵׁאוֹלָה** is derived from the root word **שָׂאֵל**, which means “to demand back.” The Ruach (spirit) of humans did not spring from the dust, and therefore it is not doomed to return to dust. Only the Nefesh (flesh) returns to the dust. The Ruach is destined to Sheol only if the Torah’s moral Laws are exploited for material gains.

Gehinnom consists of seven layers. The lowest layer is Sheol. Therefore, persons can be in Gehinnom and rise up to the higher layers away from Sheol. However, they can also sink back down the layers. The Zohar says that the Ruachim who have committed unforgivable sins are sent to Sheol and can never leave that layer. The Ruachim that are sent to Gehinnom is allowed to repent of their sins. The LORD determines which level of Gehinnom the Ruach is sent to upon the death of the Nefesh. From there, the Ruach repents from sin and moves up the levels of Gehinnom until it leaves Gehinnom and enters the Lower Waters of Heaven.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

All the nations that have not lived according to the LORD's moral laws will retreat through Gehinnom toward Sheol.

Verse Eighteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁸ For the needy will not always be forgotten, Nor the hope of the afflicted perish forever.</p>	<p>¹⁹ כִּי לֹא לְנִצָּחַת יִשְׁכַּח אֲבִיוֹן תְּקִוַּת עֲנָוִים [עֲנָוִים] תֵּאֱבֹד לְעַד :</p>

Verse Analysis

The oppressors of Israel have forgotten about the LORD because Israel was helpless to defend themselves and at the mercy of the oppressors' will. These nations are not concerned about what the LORD will do to them because the LORD's people are under their power. The Psalmist reminds us that the LORD will never forget the weak, especially Israel. The LORD will help Israel even before the coming of the day of final judgment.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

For the pauper shall not eternally be forgotten, nor shall the hope of the oppressed perish.

Verse Nineteen

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>¹⁹ Arise, O LORD, do not let man prevail; Let the nations be judged before You.</p>	<p>קוֹמָה יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי-יַעֲזֹב אֲנֹשׁ :²⁰ יִשְׁפֹּטוּ גוֹיִם עַל-פְּנֵיהֶם :</p>

Verse Analysis

The Psalmist calls out to the LORD, urging Him to warn the overbearing oppressors by intervening in history.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Arise LORD and do not let the oppressors prevail as you send Gevurah to intervene in their doing.

Verse Twenty

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>²⁰ Put them in fear, O LORD; Let the nations know that they are but men. Selah.</p>	<p>שִׁיתָהּ יְהוָה מוֹרָה לָהֶם ²¹׃ יִדְעוּ גוֹיִם אֲנֹשׁ תִּמָּה סִלָּה׃</p>

Verse Analysis

The Psalmist is asking that a spiritual and moral seed be placed in their oppressors to teach them how to return to the paths of prudence and understanding. Israel did not pray that the nations who oppressed them should perish. They prayed that their oppressors would see the evil in their ways and would return to the LORD's moral code.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

May the LORD teach and correct the nations who oppress Israel. May they stop their violence. Meditate on this verse.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the LORD, who grants Netzach in the form of immortality to the nation of Israel.
A psalm of David.

I will always praise you, LORD, and tell the nations of your wondrous works in good and bad times.

I rejoice and sing praises to your name, O most high.

When Goliath was slain, the Philistines stumbled back home because they were in fear of Gevurah. Justice for Israel was being served because of the Philistines oppression.

You have furthered my destiny and appointed Gevruah to bring the judgment seat for judging righteously.

For you have told the nations of the world that lawlessness and immorality will eventually bring Gevurah to the nation, and the nation will be erased from history.

The enemy's kingdom has come to an end forever. You destroyed their cities, and they have been removed from history and thus forgotten.

The LORD is resting until the defeat of Amalek, for when that happens, Gevurah will judge the world from His throne.

And Gevurah will judge the world and will bring order to chaos through executing judgment upon the nations.

The LORD shall become a high tower for the oppressed and afflicted and for those times of future distress.

The oppressed people who know the LORD's name shall always trust You; You have never forsaken all people who seek out your counsel and help for you.

Sing praises to the LORD who dwells in the Temple in Zion, and declare His works among the nations.

For the LORD, avenges blood has remembered them; He has not forgotten the cry of the humble.

Favor me, LORD. See my afflictions and give me a generous portion of mercy for you alone raise me above death's door.

That I may tell of Your acts and that I may take one-day rejoice within the gates of Zion, so that I may rejoice in your salvation.

Whenever a nation falls into their own evil pit, into the very snare they caught their foot in,

The LORD becomes known because He sends Gevurah to execute judgment.

Meditate on these two verses.

All the nations that have not lived according to the LORD's moral laws will retreat through Gehinnom toward Sheol.

For the pauper shall not eternally be forgotten, nor shall the hope of the oppressed perish.

Arise LORD and do not let the oppressors prevail as you send Gevurah to intervene in their doing.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

